

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE FOR PROFESSIONAL PURPOSES

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Abstract. The article considers general tendencies in world and Russian education, and also both principles and methods of forming professional, communicative, intercultural competences and in the process of teaching foreign language for professional purposes in the conditions of engineering, economic and other non-linguistic specialties at technical university.

Key words: education, pedagogical process, language teaching, communicative competence, foreign language for professional purposes.

In modern society, specialists with abilities and skills that allow a professional to be more maneuverable and successful in present conditions of market relations, carrying out effectively lots of labor activity, being at the same time quite socially adapted, is in great demand.

The purpose of the article is the need to determine the scientific and practical importance of the professional competence of the student and teacher as direct interacting initiators and participants within the educational process, its development, in turn, is a prerequisite for the further professional formation of a future specialist.

Prospects for the development of education are due to both the use of innovative methods and technologies in the meaningfulness of the educational process, and the growth of the teacher's professional competence [2, p. 109]. Recently, in psychological and pedagogical research, the issue of forming a professionally competent working specialist in any area of modern production has become particularly relevant. Within recent social environment, the model of sociopsychological of a competent specialist lays the emphasis on such personality psychological qualities as independence in solving complex problems, autonomous use of knowledge, skills, discipline, a satisfactory image of one's self; the ability to conduct coordinated communication, management of personal communication in a team, the internal need for self-development.

Great importance can be assigned to a communication process, in the implementation of one of the important functional properties of professional competence, namely, the one that integrates development of creative abilities, so ingenious communication it takes place both internally and at the intercultural

level, implying the usage of a foreign language. The new many-sided and all-around world puts forward new requirements to a successful application procedure in general and work with personnel in particular [9].

As far as a distinctive feature of the present state of affairs in various fields of economy, business is the presence of joint ventures and / or all kinds of relations with foreign partners, so it is hard to imagine communication with the personnel without a foreign language, as a means of communication. Almost everyone agrees that for modern managers, English is not a luxury, but a tool to do some efficient work in the professional sphere.

The competence can be considered as the formation of the ability, for the qualitative functioning of an employee, in the field of a particular discipline applying some special knowledge, skills, ways of thinking, awareness of responsibility for their own actions aimed at organizing and applying creative abilities in a professional sphere. Of great importance in the implementation of the functional properties of a professional and personal competence, integrating the development of creative abilities, is the communication process [8, p. 41].

The role of personal, business and professional communication, which is growing in the modern world, is manifested both in real live communication, and in a form of electronic communication via email, social networks, instant or chat messengers and their options, print, audio and even video messages, as well as internal options phone calls. The indicated possibilities of communicative resources imply the expansion of the external boundaries of communication to almost global limits. That is, participants in such a wide range of interactions need to use a foreign language to carry out both personal and industrial-business communication. Such a need entails an increase in demand for workers in the professional non-linguistic spheres such as technical, engineering, economic, which are able to carry out the communication process using knowledge of a foreign language. User functioning of a foreign language makes it possible to expand the scope of the employee's business activity. Modern requirements put forward to specialists suggest modern, innovative approaches to teaching, in particular, English [10, p. 300]. One of such approaches in teaching English may be methodological management. The effectiveness of methodological management is determined by its functions (forecasting, planning, development and decision-making, organization, control accounting), which are aimed at implementing some necessary stages of managing activity in training [3, p. 73].

Along with the increase of a number of foreign language users among the future specialists right in their professional activities, a very important issue is the prospect of fruitful interaction between a foreign language teacher and students of non-linguistic specialties in the field of the professional orientation of the learning process and as a result of improving the quality of forthcoming activities of a future specialist according to the specialty.

So, language education on a professional technical basis within non-linguistic specialties is becoming an important component which takes part in creating the effective life of a future specialist in the global multilingual and multicultural space of the human community. “English plays a large role in the life of modern students, as it is the dominant language of international communication, trade, cooperation and business. The development of modern IT technologies not only contributes to the development of a foreign language, but also emphasizes its relevance [6, p. 47].

The increase in information and communication resources in language professional training contributes to the formation of a foreign language to be a real means of communication between future specialists and foreign-language colleagues. When implementing a functional-communicative approach, specially oriented types of speech activity are developed with the aim of mastering a foreign language in line with the specifics of a future profession within the framework of developing the professional competence of students. Attracting a socio-cultural approach means the cultural development of a future young specialist, contributing to building successful business activity in the proposed conditions of intercultural communication, and an indicator of the presence of such ability is an intercultural competence, complementing the professional one from the position of inter-lingual, language-oriented professional communication in the framework of effective professional activities [9].

Functional-communicative, socio-cultural approaches and IT modern technologies involved in the formation of professionally oriented competence are focused on the student’s personal characteristics, self-improvement, and development of the individual creative potential [5, p. 408].

Specially oriented language training in the framework of non-linguistic technical, economic and other specialties gives students the opportunity to act in the future as a mediator between different languages and cultures in business and socio-cultural spheres, that is, it becomes a kind of tool for the formation of social mobility, activity and adaptability of a young specialist’s consciousness.

To accomplish such a task of social adaptation and professional self-realization, it is necessary to use an interdisciplinary approach in teaching foreign language for professional purposes, which is a coordinated, equivalent, mutually contributing interplay of educational disciplines, combined by one whole educational and didactic system.

Such an implementation of interdisciplinary relations provides the basis for the formation of communicative and professional competencies, which in turn becomes the key to high-quality teaching of a foreign language in non-linguistic specialties [1]. For example, when creating a work program with foreign language for professional purposes teaching, it should be noted that the use of a foreign language of a specialty helps to improve the professional competence of a future specialist, namely, broadens the horizons in the process of obtaining information in a foreign language and, accordingly, improves the quality and level of business or industrial sphere of communication.

Professionally-oriented language education in the conditions of a non-language educational environment is the process of developing the ability to: use an additional foreign language as a communication tool in the field of professional activity, taking into account its non-language specificity; recognize a foreign language professional culture; to build an adequate thought-out tolerant dialogue with participants in the inter-lingual process of communication [7, p. 94]. The implementation of intercultural competence presupposes the ability, of students, to maintain a communicative interaction in order to realize certain personal and professional intentions in reality, cooperate calmly within the framework of diverse situational communication. So, it is necessary to form in future specialists the ability to put into practice a foreign language interpretation of the linguistic picture of the world and specialty with a further direct and easy access into the open information and communication space of professional activities. The process of combining the perception of the world fragments through linguistically designed language of the specialty is happening by means of a foreign language as a speech tool for a fragmented expression of the original native and newly emerging, re-cognizable linguistic worldview and the specialty itself within a large communicatively designed space of modern reality [4].

Thus, linguistic education in the conditions of a non-linguistic university acts as an important instrument for the successful functioning of a person in a multilingual and multicultural community of people. In the era of the development of information technologies leading to the modernization of both

global and Russian education, it is necessary to develop new effective principles for the formation and effective coordinated implementation of communicative-language and professional competencies for foreign language for professional purposes in non-linguistic specialties and areas.

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